

Techno-economic analysis of a swimming pool heating system retrofitting through a dual source heat pump

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ABSTRACT

The European energy policies are aiming to the electrification of the heating sector as it is considered one of the solutions indicated for the decarbonization of the energy system. Heat pumps represent the most promising and widely adopted solution. However, there are some inherent technological problems to heat pumps, such as evaporator frosting for air-source heat pumps and ground thermal drift for ground source heat pumps. From this perspective a dual-source (air-geothermal) heat pumps represents a promising solution to overcome those challenges. GEOFIT H2020 project aims at developing a wide range of smart solutions for the retrofitting of thermal systems based on shallow and deep geothermal source. In this paper, the retrofitting of a gas boiler based system for the heating of a swimming pool in Galway (Ireland) with a dual-source heat pump with active regeneration of the soil is presented. Firstly, a swimming pool model developed in TRNSYS environment was validated through experimental campaign data retrieved by the Galway demo site. The baseline system composed by a gas boiler was simulated, then a reference retrofit solution composed by a dual source heat pump and an analogous system with a reduced design size were proposed and simulated for a long-term period (20 years). The analysis showed that a relevant primary energy saving is achievable and that the ground thermal drift is mitigated through the active ground heat regeneration. The techno-economic analysis revealed that the proposed system could have a replicability in retrofit solutions, especially in those with a seasonal imbalance where only heating loads are required during the whole year. Considering the current and foreseen increase of the fossil fuel costs, the economic competitiveness will be more favourable.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European energy policies are aiming to the electrification of the heating sector as it is considered one of the solutions indicated for the decarbonization of the energy system (Neirotti et al. 2020). Moreover, the strategy foresees the achievement of the 100% renewable targets for residential and tertiary purposes (Palomba et al. 2020, 2021). Toward this aim, the power to heat approaches based on heat pumps are the most promising solutions (Bloess et al. 2018). Great efforts in the research is devoted to improve the performances of heat pump components in order to make them more and more competitive. Air source heat pumps (ASHPs) ensure a low initial installation cost and have a high feasibility; however, under cold and humid weather conditions, this technology is subjected to frosting on the evaporator (Jang et al. 2013; Wang et al. 2018). When frosting occurs, a derating in terms of efficiency and heating capacity is achieved (Di Schio et al. 2021). A ground source heat pumps (GSHPs) does not present this problem, but they introduce other issues such as higher costs and technical efforts related to drilling and installation (Rivoire et al. 2018). If the GSHP has an unbalanced exploitation between heating and cooling mode, a significant thermal drift in the ground can occur over a number of years, since the energy extracted and re-injected over the season do not compensate each other. A solution proposed to solve this problem by designers foresees the significant oversize of the buried heat exchangers (Yang et al. 2013; Wang et al. 2017), thus leading to an increase of capital installation costs. The dual source solution can optimize the exploitation of both air and ground sources, thus avoiding the derating due to the evaporator frosting and the oversize of geothermal field (Corberán et al. 2018; Bottarelli 2019). The main challenge currently faced by these multi-source systems, whose experimental validation is still limited, is the correct design and operation according to the various techno-economical constraints and the environmental perspective.

In this context, GEOFIT H2020 project (GEOFIT Website) aims at developing a wide range of smart solutions for the retrofitting of thermal systems based on shallow and deep geothermal source. In this paper, the retrofitting of a gas boiler-based system for the heating of a swimming pool in Galway (Ireland) with a dual-source heat pump is presented. The system was studied by comparing the long-term performances of the baseline system, composed by a gas boiler and the swimming pool, against two innovative dual source retrofit solutions: a reference scenario and a scenario in which a dual source system with a reduced size was proposed. The swimming pool TRNSYS model was validated with the experimental data retrieved in the project demo-site located in Galway. Finally, a techno-economic analysis was performed in order to analyse the feasibility of the proposed systems.

2. MODEL DESCRIPTION

2.1 The dual source concept

The retrofitting of a swimming pool heating system composed by a gas boiler is the core of the GEOFIT concept. The new layout foresees the introduction of a dual source heat pump (HP) connected in parallel to the existing heat source (gas boiler). The heat pump works with two different sources: air and ground that are alternatively selected by the control system. Geothermal energy is exploited through vertical boreholes, aerothermal energy through an air-to-water forced convection heat exchanger, hereafter called “dry heater”. The main components of the modelled system and their connections are shown in Figure 1

Figure 1: Main components of the GEOFIT suggested retrofit system. 1-swimming pool, 2-heat pump booster heat exchanger, 3-boiler booster heat exchanger, 4-heat pump, 5-existing boiler, 6-active regeneration valve, 7-regeneration pump, 8-borehole geothermal field, 9-dual source switch valve, 10-dry heater

The dual source system foresees three different operation modes:

1. Ground mode: if $T_{air} < T_{switch}$
2. Air mode: if $T_{air} > T_{switch}$
3. Regeneration mode: if $T_{air} > T_{switch}$ AND HP switched off

Where T_{air} is the outdoor ambient air temperature and T_{switch} is a fixed reference temperature assumed equal to the ground undisturbed temperature. In ground mode the evaporation heat is extracted only from the boreholes, in air mode the evaporation heat is extracted only from the dry heater, in regeneration mode the energy extracted from ambient air is injected to the borehole through the heat transfer fluid, in order to operate an active regeneration of the ground. This phase reduces the long-term ground thermal drift that negatively affects the heat pump efficiency, furthermore, the regeneration will extend the operational lifetime of the system as it will delay the freezing conditions of an exhausted ground collector field. Switching between the operating modes occur through the valves indicated as (6) and (10) in Figure 1.

The dual source system was compared to a baseline system composed by a gas boiler.

2.2 Description of the transient model

The simulation environment chosen for the transient simulation of the described system is TRNSYS 18. The wide library of components (called types) allows to build complex systems, the control strategies are adapted for a simulation model since the replication of an accurate control loop highly responsive (with cycle times < 1 s) is out of the scope of a long-term evaluation.

In the baseline model (Figure 2) the heat generation loop is composed by a gas boiler, the supply loop by the swimming pool. The loops are physically interconnected by heat exchangers.

Figure 2: TRNSYS layout of the baseline system model.

The swimming pool model is implemented through a dedicated component of the library (type 344) that is able to replicate the dynamic evolution of indoor swimming pools. The main contributions to the heat balance of the swimming pool are summarized are listed below:

- \dot{Q}_{heat} heating power supplied by the external heating system;
- \dot{Q}_{SW} heating power due to short wave solar gains;
- \dot{Q}_{cond} heat losses due to conduction;
- \dot{Q}_{renov} heat losses due to fresh water entering the pool;
- \dot{Q}_{evap} heat losses due to water evaporation;
- \dot{Q}_{LW} heat losses due to radiative exchange with walls;
- \dot{Q}_{conv} heat losses due to convection effect.

The parameter setting and validation of the swimming pool TRNSYS type will be discussed in the next section. The flow rate supplied to the swimming pool is 220,000 kg/h, then a fixed fraction, hereafter called “booster flow rate”, fixed to 5.93% is delivered to the heating loop and heated up by a heat exchanger connected to the gas boiler generation loop. Both flow rate values were retrieved from pilot site measurement data. A forcing function type was used to set the trends of indoor temperature, relative humidity and radiant temperature of the enclosures. The swimming pool type

shows a high sensitivity behaviour when changing the listed boundary conditions. From a first measurement campaign, based on data retrieved in September 2021, the indoor temperature was oscillating between 26.5°C and 27°C, the relative humidity between 58% and 65%, the radiant temperature between 25°C and 25.5°C. The short-wave heat gain input required by the swimming pool type is due to the visible solar radiation that, transmitted through the windows, is absorbed by pool water. The Matterport virtual tool (My Matterport website), used within GEOFIT project, allows to make a 3-D tour inside the demo-site, including the technical room. This tool was used to estimate the windows surface size (Figure 3). Then, the radiation transmitted by the glass was obtained through the TRNSYS type 687 by knowing the glass wall azimuth orientation.

Figure 3: Measurement of the glass wall obtained through the Matterport tool developed within GEOFIT project

As mentioned before, in the “booster loop” the fraction of the total flow rate is 5.93% that corresponds to 13,050 kg/h.

The gas boiler was simulated by means of type 700, the temperature outlet set-point was fixed to 70°C and the overall boiler efficiency is set to 0.74 as calculated during the experiment of heating the swimming pool and gas measurements. A simple thermostat (type1502) checks the water temperature of the swimming pool and activates the gas boiler when heating is required, the thermostat is set to 28.5°C with a dead band of $\pm 0.25^\circ\text{C}$. A PID controller attempt to maintain the pool water temperature at the set-point fixed to 28.5°C by varying the flow rate in the primary side of the heat exchanger through a diverter valve.

As represented in Figure 1, in the retrofit model, the geothermal system was connected in parallel with the described existing one that, in the TRNSYS interface, is grouped in a macro (Figure 4).

Figure 4: TRNSYS layout of the retrofit system model

The heat pump was modelled through the set of expressions, showed in equations [1-7], obtained from the datasheet provided by the technology supplier. This approach allows to calculate the condensation and evaporation heat and thermodynamic COP by knowing the evaporation (source) and condensation (sink) inlet temperature of the heat transfer fluid. The flow rate is varied on both source and sink side in order to keep a fixed temperature difference between inlet and outlet of each component, as suggested by the supplier (equations [6-7]). In TRNSYS, these calculation formulas were implemented into a calculator type.

$$\dot{Q} = f(T_{inlet}, T_{outlet}) \quad [1]$$

$$COP = f(T_{inlet}, T_{outlet}) \quad [2]$$

$$T_{source,out} = T_{source,in} - \Delta T_{source} \quad [3]$$

$$\dot{m}_{sink} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{sink}}{c_p \cdot \Delta T_{sink}} \quad [4]$$

$$\dot{m}_{source} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{source}}{c_p \cdot \Delta T_{source}} \quad [5]$$

$$\Delta T_{source} = 3 \text{ K} \quad [6]$$

$$\Delta T_{sink} = 10 \text{ K} \quad [7]$$

The heat pump operation is always on heating mode since it supplies only the swimming pool throughout the year. The thermostat (type 1502) that monitors the pool water temperature activates the heat pump when heating is required. The heat pump thermostat set-point is set to 28.5°C with a centred dead band of 0.5 K, the thermostat set-point of the backup gas boiler is set to 27.9 with a centred dead band of 0.5 K. When the heat request is major than the heat pump capacity, the pool water temperature falls down, at 27.65°C the gas boiler is activated and rise up the temperature, thus avoiding to reach temperature out of the prescribed range.

The borehole geothermal field was modelled by type 557, based on Duct Storage (DST) model (TESS 2014). It is defined as a system in which heat is stored directly in the ground, a duct or channel system is used for transferring heat between a heat carrier fluid which circulates through the ducts and the ground storage. The storage volume has the shape of a cylinder with vertical symmetry axis. The ducts are assumed to be uniformly distributed within the storage volume. Convective heat transfer in the ducts and conductive heat transfer in the ground is assumed. A geothermal field composed by “U-shape” (single closed loop collectors) boreholes was chosen, the surrounding ground is composed by meta-gabbro rock as per the Geological Survey of Ireland bedrock characterisation map. The retrieved heat transfer properties were compared and validated

with those presented by (Dalla Santa et al. 2020). The heat transfer fluid is composed by a mixture of water and ethanol with a mass ratio of 40% of ethanol. The heat losses or heat gains along the buried pipelines that connect the borehole field to the manifold of heat pump could affect the overall efficiency of system, so they were considered by configuring the type 952. The dry heater that works as air source device was modelled through type 508 and it is configured using a bypass approach in which the user specifies a fraction of the air stream that bypasses the coil. The remainder of the air stream is assumed to exit the coil at the average temperature of the fluid in the coil and at saturated conditions. The type is able to maintain the fluid outlet temperature below the user specified maximum, in this case a difference of temperature between inlet and outlet water temperature was set to 6K.

As previously explained, the retrofit solution foresees a dual source operation mode. In TRNSYS model, the following logic controls were implemented to set-up the dual source operation:

- the **air mode** is activated when $T_{air} > T_{switch}$, with reference to the component numbers indicated in Figure 1, the flow on the source side follows the following path: 4, 9, 10, 6, 4;
- the **ground mode** is activated when $T_{air} < T_{switch}$, with reference to the component numbers indicated in Figure 1, the flow on the source side follows the following path: 4, 9, 8, 6, 4;
- the **regeneration mode** is activated when $T_{air} > T_{switch}$ and the HP is off (there is no heating demand from swimming pool), the regeneration pump is turned on. With reference to the component numbers indicated in Figure 1, the flow on the source side follows the following path: 7,6,10,9,8,7. In this way an active regeneration of the ground is performed (the energy is delivered from the air to the ground) that supports the natural one.

The behaviour of the described systems was simulated by considering Galway (Ireland) as reference location, since it is the selected city that will host the experimental demo-site of GEOFIT project. In Table 1 the monthly values of average air temperature and solar irradiation for this location are reported. Weather data file were retrieved by Meteonorm database (Database), the standard file format “.tm2” was used.

Table 1: monthly climatic data for Galway (Ireland)

Month	Average outdoor temperature [°C]	Solar irradiation [kWh/m ²]
January	5.7	19
February	5.6	30
March	6.8	67
April	8.5	115
May	11.2	140
June	13.8	142
July	14.8	124
August	14.9	97
September	13.3	78
October	10.3	48
November	7.8	22
December	5.6	15
Year	9.9	894

The T_{switch} , assumed equal to the ground undisturbed temperature, is calculated by type 557 by considering the climatic data. For the selected location, the resulting value is $T_{switch} = 10^{\circ}\text{C}$

A simulation time of 20 years was selected to evaluate the response of the system to the ground thermal drift, the simulation time step was fixed to 1 hour.

3. POOL MODEL VALIDATION AND DESIGN

The monitoring system installed in the Galway demo-site provides with all the data necessary to validate the TRNSYS swimming pool loop model and allowed us to calculate the design parameters of the retrofitted solution.

Monitoring data were mainly used for calibration of the parameters of the swimming pool type and the booster heat exchanger ones. Data available for the entire month of September 2021 was chosen for the model validation. The model inputs from the experimental data were:

- indoor air temperature and humidity provided as input to the type 344 (swimming pool);
- temperature and flow rate on the primary side of the heat exchanger (boiler side) provided as input to type 91 (booster heat exchanger).

TRNSYS types parameters were changed until a match between temperature outlet from heat exchanger and swimming pool comparable to those measured in the demo-site was found. Then, the heating energy required from the swimming pool in the demo-site was compared to that one calculated by the TRNSYS model. The results show a very good matching for the swimming pool temperature. Figure 5(a) shows an operational profile of 7 days of operation. The comparison of heating energy exchanged in the booster heat exchanger shows a good matching between measured and simulated values with a deviation of -3% with respect to the measured values for 15 operation days (Figure 5b).

Figure 5: (a) comparison between pool temperature measured and simulated for 7 days of operation. (b) comparison between the measured and simulated heating energy required by the swimming pool within a range of 15 operation days

The obtained validation allows evaluating the average heat loss by the swimming pool ranging around 35kW and the daily heating energy required ranging about 850 kWh. These outcomes were the input data to design the nominal size of heat pump and borehole field. The monthly energy requirement is indicated in Figure 6. The selected reference heat pump has the following nominal performances ($T_{source}=12^{\circ}C/9^{\circ}C$, $T_{sink}=35^{\circ}C/45^{\circ}C$): $\dot{Q}_{sink}=58.6$ kW, $\dot{Q}_{source}=46.3$ kW, COP=4.28. A geothermal field composed by 9 “U-shape” boreholes 150 m deep was chosen. Then, for the techno-economic evaluation, a second scenario was considered in which a heat pump with a heat capacity reduced to the 60% of the reference one was selected and a geothermal field composed by 5 boreholes 150 m deep was chosen. Both scenarios were compared with the baseline system results. The auxiliaries consumption in the retrofit systems is fixed to 20% of heat pump consumption as assessed by (Dino et al. 2021)

Figure 6: monthly energy load requested by the swimming pool

4. SIMULATION RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The main outcomes of the simulation performed for a long-term period consist in the evaluation of the global yearly energy consumption and in the comparison

between the baseline scenario and the retrofit solutions. The baseline system (in which only the gas boiler is installed) foresees only one energy source that is the natural gas. For both retrofit solutions proposed, the system requires two different energy sources: electricity and natural gas, so the comparative consumption analysis was performed evaluating the primary energy consumption, hence, the average primary energy factors for Ireland showed in Table 2 were considered (SEAI).

Table 2: primary energy factors

Energy source	Primary energy factor
Electricity	1.83
Natural gas	1.1

The global results related to the entire simulation period shows that in the reference dual source solution the heat pump is correctly designed to supply to whole energy demand of the swimming pool since there is no natural gas consumption. When passing from the reference dual source system to the reduced one there is a slight decrease in the electricity consumption and a natural gas consumption since the heat pump is undersized for the peak demand of the swimming pool (Figure 7a).

The reduced capacity of the heat pump designed in the retrofit solution induces a periodical activation of the gas boiler. Due to the cascade temperature control actuated by the heat pump thermostat and to the gas boiler one described in par. 2.2, the average pool temperature is slightly lower in this scenario, although maintaining the pool temperature within the prescribed limits. This leads to lower heat losses by the swimming pool and, consequently, lower heating demand.

The comparison in terms of primary energy shows that the retrofit solution lets to achieve a primary energy saving of 39% and 49% respectively for the reference and reduced dual source system (Figure 7b).

Figure 7: a)-energy consumption for the simulated period (20 years) detailed for each energy source and scenario - b) primary energy consumption and primary energy saving for each scenario

The ground temperature profile is shown in Figure 8, the oscillating trend is due to the dual operation and to the active regeneration of the ground. This technological solution enables mitigating the thermal drift of the ground, thus enhancing the performances of heat pump. With reference to the entire simulation period the resulting thermal drift is 4.4 K for the reference dual source system and 5.6 K for the reduced retrofit system. The electrical energy consumption required to operate the regeneration mode (due to the dry heater and regeneration pump) reaches up to 3% of the overall electrical energy consumption in the reference dual source case and is lower than 1% for the reduced one.

Figure 8: ground temperature trend for the simulated scenarios

5. TECHNO-ECONOMIC ANALYSIS

A techno economic analysis was performed in order to give a perspective of feasibility and replicability of the proposed retrofit solutions even considering the increase of the energy costs, strictly related to international and political instabilities as well as new energy policies implemented. A reference indicator considered for the present analysis is the simple payback time expressed as

$$\text{Payback} = \frac{\text{CAPEX}}{\text{CASHFLOW}} \quad [8]$$

in which CAPEX indicates the capital expenditure necessary to install the proposed retrofit solution and CASHFLOW indicate is the yearly result of the difference between the operating costs (OPEX) of baseline system and the retrofit one, thus indicating the avoided expenditures. A market analysis conducted as part of the GEOFIT project was taken as the estimation of CAPEX for the retrofit solution. The cost magnitude of the main components cost including of supply and install are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Cost rates for the main components of the retrofit system, as assessed in the GEOFIT project

Component	Cost
Vertical boreholes	68.10 €/m
Buried horizontal pipeline: boreholes to manifold	52.00 €/m
Buried horizontal pipeline: manifold to plant room	176.00 €/m
Hydronic heat pump	560.00 €/kW
Dry heater	276.00 €/kW

The main cost rates, especially the costs related to drilling and installation of boreholes were compared to that suggested by (Pokhrel et al. 2022) finding a reliable assessment. The final CAPEX for reference and reduced retrofit scenarios are indicated in Table 4, the costs for auxiliaries, engineering, legal costs, electronic control systems and civil works are also included.

Table 4: CAPEX of the proposed retrofit solutions

Scenario	CAPEX
Reference	329 k€
Reduced	251 k€

The OPEX (Table 5) are composed by the energy costs retrieved by the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) by referring to the last available data for electricity and natural gas (2021 Q2), furthermore a carbon tax for natural gas was applied as prescribed by Irish authorities (Irish tax and customs), the final natural gas cost is the sum of market price and carbon tax. The maintenance costs were considered comparable for

both baseline and retrofit solutions, thus they were neglected.

Table 5: OPEX based on cost of energy

Energy source	Cost rates
Electricity	17.16 cents €/kWh
Natural gas	3.49 cents €/kWh
Natural gas carbon tax	6.72 cents €/kWh

In order to appreciate the techno-economic feasibility of the retrofit system, a wide spectrum of cases were modelled in which the electricity cost and natural gas cost energy component were varied between -50% to +50% with reference to the actual costs showed in

Table 5, the carbon tax was considered constant. The results show payback times lower than 20 years if considering the actual cost of energy, this can be lowered if an increase of natural gas cost will occur (Figure 9). Between the two retrofit solutions the reduced one is the best performing solution in terms of payback time: 9 years against 12.8 years. It is worthy to notice that the reference solution simulation results showed a null natural gas consumption thus leading to avoid maintaining active the existing baseline system. Furthermore, the reduced size geothermal field lead to a higher ground temperature drift (Figure 8).

Figure 9: payback time for reference a) and reduced b) proposed retrofit solutions by considering the variation of electricity and natural gas cost variation. The green circle indicates the payback time with actual costs

6 CONCLUSIONS

The dual source heat pumps are a promising technology that can achieve high performances and help solve technological and economic issues of single ASHPs and GSHPs. The GEOFIT project proposes a dual source air/ground heat pump that will supply heating to a swimming pool located in Galway, Ireland. To avoid an excessive ground thermal drift an active regeneration of the soil is proposed. This system is analysed through a transient simulation software (TRNSYS) and validated with experimental by comparison with the baseline heating system composed by a gas boiler. Two retrofit scenarios were proposed: (1) a dual source heat pump with its geothermal field designed to supply the entire heating demand of swimming pool and (2) a reduced size system. Both are connected in parallel to the existing system in order to operate the gas boiler when supplementary heat is needed. Both retrofit systems showed a reduction of primary energy consumption. The active regeneration considered effectively mitigates the thermal drift in the geothermal field. Finally, a techno-economic analysis was carried on by considering a wide range of variation of energy cost. This showed simple payback times lower than 20 years if considering the actual costs, this

value can be lowered if an increase of the natural gas cost is supposed.

The obtained results showed that the dual source system proposed by the GEOFIT project is a promising solution for the retrofit of existing gas-fired systems that can become more attractive if considering the actual energy price volatility scenario (March 2022) in Europe, but also if a sustained increase in price is considered.

REFERENCES

Bloess A, Schill WP, Zerrahn A (2018) Power-to-heat for renewable energy integration: A review of technologies, modeling approaches, and flexibility potentials. *Appl. Energy* 212:1611–1626

Bottarelli M (2019) Testing of a dual-source heat pump coupled with flat-panel ground heat exchangers. *Int J Low-Carbon Technol* 14:247–255. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijlct/ctz004>

Corberán JM, Cazorla-Marín A, Marchante-Avellaneda J, Montagud C (2018) Dual source heat pump, a high efficiency and cost-effective

- alternative for heating, cooling and DHW production. *Int J Low-Carbon Technol* 13:161–176. <https://doi.org/10.1093/IJLCT/CTY008>
- Dalla Santa G, Galgaro A, Sassi R, et al (2020) An updated ground thermal properties database for GSHP applications. *Geothermics* 85:101758. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GEOTHERMICS.2019.101758>
- Database M Meteororm Version 8 - Meteororm (en). <https://meteororm.com/en/meteororm-version-8>. Accessed 4 Mar 2021
- Di Schio ER, Ballerini V, Dongellini M, Valdiserri P (2021) Defrosting of air-source heat pumps: Effect of real temperature data on seasonal energy performance for different locations in Italy. *Appl Sci* 11:1178003. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app11178003>
- Dino GE, Palomba V, Calderoni M, Brebels A (2021) Long term performance simulation of a dual source heat pump. *ECOS 2021 - Proc 34rd Int Conf Effic Cost, Optim Simul Environ Impact Energy Syst*
- GEOFIT Website Geofit project. <https://geofit-project.eu/>
- Irish tax and customs Rate of tax. <https://www.revenue.ie/en/companies-and-charities/excise-and-licences/energy-taxes/natural-gas-carbon-tax/rate-of-tax.aspx>. Accessed 10 Mar 2022
- Jang JY, Bae HH, Lee SJ, Ha MY (2013) Continuous heating of an air-source heat pump during defrosting and improvement of energy efficiency. *Appl Energy* 110:9–16. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APENERGY.2013.04.030>
- My Matterport website No Title
- Neirotti F, Noussan M, Simonetti M (2020) Towards the electrification of buildings heating - Real heat pumps electricity mixes based on high resolution operational profiles. *Energy* 195:116974. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.116974>
- Palomba V, Borri E, Charalampidis A, et al (2021) An Innovative Solar-Biomass Energy System to Increase the Share of Renewables in Office Buildings. *Energies* 14:914. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14040914>
- Palomba V, Borri E, Charalampidis A, et al (2020) Implementation of a solar-biomass system for multi-family houses: Towards 100% renewable energy utilization. *Renew Energy* 166:190–209. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2020.11.126>
- Pokhrel S, Amiri L, Poncet S, et al (2022) Renewable heating solutions for buildings; a techno-economic comparative study of sewage heat recovery and Solar Borehole Thermal Energy Storage System. *Energy Build* 259:111892. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2022.111892>
- Rivoire M, Casasso A, Piga B, Sethi R (2018) Assessment of energetic, economic and environmental performance of ground-coupled heat pumps. *Energies* 11:11081941. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en11081941>
- SEAI Conversion Factors | SEAI Statistics | SEAI. <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/conversion-factors/>. Accessed 28 Mar 2022a
- SEAI Prices | Energy Statistics In Ireland | SEAI. <https://www.seai.ie/data-and-insights/seai-statistics/key-statistics/prices/#comp00005cb739ab0000000838246e>. Accessed 10 Mar 2022b
- TESS (2014) TESSLibs 17. 06:161–165
- Wang E, Zhang F, Zhang Y, Zhao Q (2017) Influence Investigation of Thermal Load Imbalance on Geothermal Heat Exchanger. *Procedia Eng* 205:3846–3851. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.PROENG.2017.10.072>
- Wang F, Liang C, Zhang X (2018) Research of anti-frosting technology in refrigeration and air conditioning fields: A review. *Renew Sustain Energy Rev* 81:707–722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.RSER.2017.08.046>
- Yang W, Chen Y, Shi M, Spittler JD (2013) Numerical investigation on the underground thermal imbalance of ground-coupled heat pump operated in cooling-dominated district. *Appl Therm Eng* 51:626–637. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.APPLTHERMALENG.2013.04.061>

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